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Kynurenine: an inflammation marker in autoimmunity

Kynurenine

The amino acid kynurenine is little known in the wider public despite its crucial role in endocrinology. It is produced in the body through the breakdown of tryptophan, another essential amino acid and is involved in several important biological processes, including the synthesis of neurotransmitters, the regulation of immune function, and the metabolism of nitrogen. In the body, tryptophan is converted into kynurenine by the enzyme tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase (TDO). This process occurs in the liver and is regulated by hormones and other signaling molecules. The kynurenine pathway is a major route for the metabolism of tryptophan, and it is involved in several important physiological processes. One important role of kynurenine is in the synthesis of neurotransmitters, such as serotonin and melatonin. Serotonin is a neurotransmitter that plays a key role in mood regulation, and melatonin is a hormone involved in the regulation of sleep. Kynurenine is also involved in the synthesis of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD), a molecule that plays a crucial role in energy metabolism and the production of ATP. In addition to its role in neurotransmitter synthesis, kynurenine is also involved in the regulation of immune

function. It can act as an immune modulator, and high levels of kynurenine have been linked to inflammation and autoimmune disorders. Kynurenine is also involved in the metabolism of nitrogen, which is an essential element for the synthesis of many types of proteins and other biomolecules. The kynurenine pathway plays a key role in the nitrogen cycle, which is the process by which nitrogen is converted into different chemical forms and incorporated into living organisms. Overall, kynurenine is a multifunctional molecule that plays important roles in several biological processes. It is produced in the body through the breakdown of tryptophan and is involved in neurotransmitter synthesis, immune regulation, and nitrogen metabolism.^{5,6,14-8}

Kynurenine pathway

The kynurenine pathway is a metabolic pathway that plays a crucial role in the metabolism of the amino acid tryptophan. Tryptophan is an essential amino acid that is obtained from the diet and is involved in a variety of physiological processes, including the synthesis of neurotransmitters like serotonin and melatonin. The kynurenine pathway begins with the conversion of

tryptophan to kynurenine by the enzyme tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase. This reaction requires the presence of oxygen and the enzyme is regulated by a number of factors, including the level of tryptophan in the body and the activity of the enzyme indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase. Kynurenine is then further metabolized through a series of reactions to produce a number of important compounds, including kynurenic acid, 3-hydroxykynurenine, and quinolinic acid. These compounds are produced through the action of enzymes such as kynureninase and kynurenine 3-monooxygenase. Kynurenic acid is an antagonist at the glycine site of the N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor and has been shown to have neuroprotective effects. 3-Hydroxykynurenine is a precursor to quinolinic acid, which is a potent agonist at the NMDA receptor and has been implicated in the development of neurodegenerative diseases. The kynurenine pathway is regulated by a number of factors, including hormonal and immune signals, and is involved in a variety of physiological processes, such as the regulation of sleep, mood, and many aspects of the cognitive function. Dysregulation of the kynurenine pathway has been linked to a number of diseases and disorders, including depression, anxiety, and neurodegenerative diseases. In addition, the kynurenine pathway is also involved in the host defense against infections, as the enzymes IDO and TDO are induced during inflammation and are thought to play a role in the suppression of T cell proliferation.^{1,2,4,6,7,8,9,11-18}

Kynurenine in autoimmunity

The kynurenine pathway has been implicated in the pathogenesis of autoimmune disorders, including multiple sclerosis (MS) and rheumatoid arthritis (RA). The enzymes indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO) and tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase (TDO) are upregulated during inflammation and are thought to play a role in the suppression of T cell proliferation, which is a key feature of autoimmune disorders.

In MS, the kynurenine pathway has been shown to be upregulated in both the central nervous system (CNS) and peripheral immune cells, leading to increased production of quinolinic acid and other neurotoxic kynurenine metabolites. These neurotoxic metabolites have been shown to contribute to the neuroinflammatory and neurodegenerative processes that occur in MS.

In RA, the kynurenine pathway has also been shown to be upregulated, leading to increased production of kynurenine and other metabolites. The upregulation of the kynurenine pathway has been associated with increased inflammation and joint damage in RA. In addition, the kynurenine pathway has been shown to play a role in the regulation of T cell activation and differentiation, which may contribute to the autoimmune response in RA.

Kynurenine-to-tryptophan ratio

The kynurenine-to-tryptophan ratio (KTR) is a measure of the balance between the kynurenine pathway and the tryptophan pathway in the body. The KTR is typically calculated by dividing the concentration of kynurenine in the blood by the concentration of tryptophan in the blood. Elevated KTRs have been observed in a number of autoimmune disorders, including multiple sclerosis (MS), rheumatoid arthritis (RA), and systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE). The elevated KTRs in these disorders are thought to be due to the upregulation of (IDO) and (TDO), which are responsible for the conversion of tryptophan to kynurenine. Elevated KTRs have been associated with increased inflammation and immune activation in autoimmune disorders. In addition, elevated KTRs have been linked to impaired cognition and mood disorders in patients with autoimmune disorders. Targeting the kynurenine pathway and reducing the KTR has been proposed as a therapeutic approach for the treatment of autoimmune disorders.^{2,3,4,5,14-18}

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

Sources

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